

The ENLIGHT project - Biological Impact of Light Pollution on Crested Newts

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Abstract: The European Commission has identified light pollution as a rapidly spreading environmental change, yet a comprehensive regulatory framework across the EU is still lacking, partly due to limited data on its impacts on wildlife. The loss of natural darkness caused by artificial light at night (ALAN) places substantial pressure on biological systems. Because amphibians represent the most threatened group of vertebrates, understanding ALAN as a component of urbanization is essential for explaining their ongoing population declines. The ENLIGHT project examines the effects of long-term exposure to LED lighting at night on two crested newt species, *Triturus ivanbureschi* and *T. macedonicus*. We test environmentally realistic ALAN intensities and track responses across larval and juvenile stages, including delayed effects through ontogenetic carry-over mechanisms and potential hormesis. We also assess whether warm (2700 K) or cold (6000 K) LED light produces fewer negative effects. Our multilevel assessment includes developmental and survival metrics, metabolic rates, diel activity patterns, corticosterone levels, and oxidative status. In parallel, the project aims to raise public awareness of light pollution and promote amphibian conservation actions. The knowledge generated will contribute to evidence-based guidelines for managing light pollution. Overall, our findings show that although both light types influence the measured traits, high-intensity cold LED light (30 lx) produced the strongest effects. Between the two species, *T. ivanbureschi* showed greater sensitivity to ALAN. These results highlight the complex biological impacts of ALAN on amphibians and reinforce the need to incorporate light pollution into conservation strategies.

Keywords: amphibians; light pollution; artificial light at night; led; newt.

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